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Synthesis Report of Local Meetings

Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative

Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Synthesis Report of Local Meetings

INTRODUCTION

The Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC), one of five LCCs in progress or planned for Alaska, was recently launched in 2010 in an early pilot stage. The Western AK LCC will share expertise and capacity to achieve common landscape conservation goals. The LCC will bring together federal, state, tribal, and local governments, academia, and other partners to develop tools, synthesize information, and provide a forum for collaboration to land and resource managers to understand and respond to climate change.

One of the first activities of the Western AK LCC was to convene a series of local meetings throughout the region to gather input on LCC directions. This report summarizes common themes and suggestions for the LCC that emerged from the local meetings.

ABOUT THE LOCAL MEETINGS

Western AK LCC staff held a series of nine (9) meetings in October and November 2010 throughout the western Alaska region to speak with potential partners and solicit input on early directions for the LCC. Meetings were held in Cold Bay, King Salmon, Dillingham, Anchorage, Kodiak, Bethel, Fairbanks, Kotzebue, and Nome.

More information about the local meetings, including the schedule, agendas, and meeting notes, can be found through the LCC meetings website at: <http://www.arcus.org/western-alaska-lcc/local-meetings>. A compilation of the final meeting notes is also included in Appendix A of this report.

Map of the Western AK LCC Region

Over 100 people participated in the series of local meetings, including representatives of federal and state agency staff, non-profit organizations, Alaska Native organizations, academia, and local residents. A list of local meeting participants is included in Appendix B.

The Western Alaska LCC is committed to collaborating with partners in order to build on each other's efforts. The Rapid Ecoregional Assessment (REA) process, led by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM), is a complementary effort that will provide additional insight on

important management questions in the northern region of the LCC. The LCC local meetings in Fairbanks, Kotzebue, and Nome were held in conjunction with the REA to avoid duplication of effort. More information about the REA, including the REA local meeting notes, can be found at:

<http://www.blm.gov/wo/st/en/prog/more/climatechange/reas/seward.html>.

SUMMARY HIGHLIGHTS FROM LOCAL MEETING DISCUSSIONS

In each of the meetings, LCC staff presented general information about Landscape Conservation Cooperatives and then input was solicited on several topics related to the LCC effort.

Several overarching and common themes emerged from the discussions; these are summarized below in the following categories: Observed Biological and Landscape Changes, Data and Information Needs, Collaboration Needs, Communication and Outreach Needs, and Other Issues.

An "issues matrix" of input provided by local meeting participants is included in Appendix C, which provides an at-a-glance summary of topics discussed.

Observed Biological and Landscape Changes

Scientists and local residents are observing landscape and ecosystem changes throughout Western Alaska in the terrestrial and marine domains. Many of these changes are of considerable concern to Alaskan communities due to their impacts on subsistence and living conditions. Listed below are several landscape changes discussed by meeting participants.

Caribou: Declining caribou populations and changing migration patterns have been observed throughout the region. These changes in caribou populations are a significant concern to resource managers and local residents, given the subsistence and cultural importance of the species.

Hydrology: Hydrological changes, specifically drying ponds and wetlands, have been observed; these changes have potential impacts to wildlife habitat quality and quantity.

Coastal Erosion: Coastal erosion is being observed in several villages in the region and is an important concern due to impacts to housing and infrastructure.

Cold Bay, Alaska

Vegetation Changes: A variety of vegetation changes are being observed in Western Alaska. Meeting participants specifically noted an increase in shrub growth (e.g., alder and willow) in current tundra areas, which may signify a loss of caribou habitat.

New or Introduced Species: Several meeting participants mentioned sightings of species formerly not seen in an area (e.g., skates present in a bay and beaver on the Seward Peninsula), or new behaviors (e.g., more overwintering Brant), as well as introduced (e.g., Bison in Kodiak area) or invasive species.

Other Observations of Change: Other observations of biological or landscape changes that were mentioned in the local meetings include changes in fish populations (e.g., declining catches in halibut and salmon), wind and weather changes, and changes in the marine environment (e.g., ocean acidification, seal population distribution changes and disease). It was also noted that human activities (e.g., energy development, deforestation) should be included when considering regional landscape change.

Data and Information Needs

A significant portion of the local meeting discussions focused on data and information needs for informed decision-making and resource management.

Baseline Data and Monitoring of Key Species and Habitat: Several participants stressed a large gap in—and critical need for—baseline data and ongoing monitoring of species and habitat, especially for subsistence species such as caribou and salmon. Participants expressed a need for long-term data that can be used to detect and understand landscape changes at scales useful for decision-making.

Habitat and Species Models: Meeting participants generally agreed on the need for habitat and species models to predict how climate change will affect the distribution, range, and habitat of species (specifically subsistence species). Development of these models and translation of the resulting information to decision-makers will require collaboration across disciplines and geographic regions.

Climate Patterns and Changes at Local and Regional Scales: Another information need discussed was downscaling of climate change models and predictions at regional and local scales. Local communities and decision-makers expressed the need to understand how climate change and other drivers will affect their local landscapes in the next decades.

Subsistence Use and Trends: Subsistence use of landscape resources is a critical issue throughout Western Alaska, and meeting participants noted the need for more information on subsistence patterns, as well as better information on how the distribution and abundance of subsistence species may change in the future. Specific information needs include potential changes in travel distances for subsistence harvest and adaptation of subsistence patterns to changes in species.

Hydrological Data and Mapping: Hydrological data was discussed as a key information gap in understanding changes in the hydrological cycle as well as potential impacts on wildlife and water resources. Specific examples of hydrological data needs include expansion of hydrological monitoring stations and mapping of lake boundaries.

Permafrost: Permafrost data was cited as a need for understanding how climate change is affecting permafrost and how those changes may impact hydrology, coastal erosion, vegetation patterns, and infrastructure.

Geospatial Baseline Mapping: Baseline mapping was also discussed as a basic data need, including coastline/erosion mapping, topographic data and elevation models, and satellite and aerial photography.

Other: Other information needs that were discussed included: wildlife contaminants and disease, human impacts and development (e.g., population growth, energy development), ocean acidification, the ocean-land interface (e.g., shoreline and intertidal processes), climate change effects on public health, fire frequency and severity, and pests and invasive species.

Collaboration Needs

There are urgent needs for integrated landscape-level observations and modeling, yet no one agency or organization has the capacity to meet these needs. Many local meeting participants recognized the value of the LCC in facilitating improved collaboration and leveraging of existing efforts and resources. Several specific suggestions for collaborative needs and activities are listed below.

Clearinghouse to Discover, Exchange, and Access Information and Data: One of the most frequent suggestions was for the development of an online portal or clearinghouse where relevant information and data could be found, including search and discovery of scientific data, information on ongoing and planned projects, publications, and a directory of experts. This would provide "one-stop-shopping" for a variety of audiences to learn about, and better coordinate with, LCC-related efforts.

Improved Coordination Within and Between State and Federal Agencies: Several meeting participants suggested improved coordination of science activities and data collection within and between state and federal agencies, as well improved communication and collaboration overall.

Collaboration on Monitoring Protocols and Joint Field Planning: Participants noted that scientific collaboration would be strengthened by coordinating monitoring protocols and joint field efforts; for example, collaboration in monitoring sites would result in complementary studies with improved spatial and geographic coverage.

Fully Integrate Indigenous Knowledge and Participation of Local Residents: Local residents emphasized the need for the LCC to fully integrate Traditional Ecological

Knowledge (TEK)/Indigenous Knowledge as a core component of science activities. In addition, the LCC was encouraged to engage in two-way communication with local residents from the beginning to end of LCC activities.

Define Clear Roles and Structure of the LCC: Since several organizations and agencies are conducting or planning efforts relevant to LCC goals, meeting participants stressed the need to clearly define and communicate the activities and structure of the LCC as well as its role in relation to existing agency efforts and programs.

Include NGOs and Other Non-Federal/State Entities in the LCC Process and Structure: In order for the LCC to be viewed as a truly collaborative effort, it was suggested that the LCC fully include non-governmental organizations (NGOs), Alaska Native organizations, and other groups in the LCC organizational structure.

Communication and Outreach Needs

Several suggestions related to communication and outreach of LCC activities and science.

Public Outreach: Several meeting participants discussed the need to provide local communities and Alaskan residents information on science and resource management that is easily understandable and can be used to inform decision-making. A related suggestion was to make a concerted effort to engage and inform the broader public/taxpayers on the value of the LCC and its relevance.

Outreach to Agencies, Policy-Makers, and the Science Community: Specific suggestions for outreach to the scientific, agency, and resource management communities included a brochure geared to upper-level policy-makers, a newsletter, and regular communications on LCC activities.

K-12 and College Student Outreach and Training: Another outreach suggestion was to engage students through targeted educational activities to encourage science as a career, or LCC internships.

Other Issues

Other input provided through the local meetings focused on LCC organizational issues, including the following suggestions:

- The LCC should ensure that long-term funding will exist for LCC activities; this should be communicated to potential partners and collaborators to encourage participation in the effort.
- The LCC should design LCC decision-making processes (selecting of committee representatives and working groups, funding decisions, etc.) to be clear and transparent, and the decision-making processes should be communicated to those outside the LCC structure.

- The LCC should consider ways to provide information to decision-makers that can facilitate decisions in the short-term; science and research can be a long process, but decision-makers need information immediately.

NEXT STEPS

The series of local meetings convened by Western Alaska LCC staff provided an excellent forum for discussing community needs throughout the region. The issues raised and discussed in the local meetings will be reviewed and discussed by the LCC interim Steering Committee and will help formulate the agenda and goals for a Western AK LCC science workshop to be held in April 2011. This science workshop will bring together land and resource managers (from state, federal, and Native Alaskan management entities), field specialists, researchers, conservation organizations, academia, and others to help identify early science needs for the new Western Alaska LCC.

More information on the Western Alaska LCC can be found through the LCC website at: <http://www.arcus.org/western-alaska-lcc>.

Appendix A. Summary Notes from Local Meetings

The Western Alaska LCC is committed to collaborating with partners in order to build on each other's efforts. The Rapid Ecoregional Assessment (REA) process, led by the Bureau of Land Management (BLM), is a complementary effort that will provide additional insight on important management questions in the northern region of the LCC. The LCC local meetings in Fairbanks, Kotzebue, and Nome were held in conjunction with the REA to avoid duplication of effort. More information about the REA, including the REA local meeting notes, can be found at: <http://www.blm.gov/wo/st/en/prog/more/climatechange/reas/seward.html>.

Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Meeting Cold Bay, Alaska 5 October 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK LCC Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion

A. What Are Your Observations of Landscape or Species Changes? Participants were asked to discuss any changes they have observed in the landscape or wildlife:

- *Drying/lower water level of ponds* – Have seen more drying ponds this year (and different ponds) than past years (perhaps due to precipitation changes this year?). One participant noted that drying like this was not evident a few decades ago and this is one of the most evident of recent landscape changes. Another long-term resident noted that the drying seems to go in cycles and that this pattern has occurred before.
- *Caribou* – One participant noted that the most dramatic impact he has seen is in decline in caribou in recent years.
 - It was noted that from a refuge management standpoint, this is a critical issue – to understand caribou population and predator dynamics, forage availability and use, etc. – need good monitoring activities.
- *Fish* – Halibut fishing not as productive (and smaller fish) in recent years. Salmon runs have been later the last few years, and poor silver salmon run this year. Unsure of anyone doing fish surveys. Skates are now present in the bay, where they had not been seen before.
- *Winds* – One noticeable change has been wind direction, which historically was SE/NW, whereas now see more easterly winds.

- *Other* – No observations noted of obvious shrub or other vegetation changes, or obvious increases in invasive species. Reports from other western Alaska villages that residents are seeing bird species they had not seen before. Local glaciers might be good indicators of landscape change – perhaps look at historical aerial photographs and compare to today (one participant has a contact person for this, will provide after meeting). Cold weather came in this year about 3 weeks earlier than usual and it seemed to be a colder winter than normal. Also seemed to have a late spring.

B. Suggestions for Other Groups and Potential Partners? Participants were asked for suggestions on other organizations, agencies, or groups that the LCC should be aware of as potential partners:

- King Cove Corporation
- Overall, need improved cooperation between state and federal agencies
- Good cooperation currently between state and federal refuges, could build on that
- Important to entrain residents who can provide observations from a long-term view
- Clarify relationships/activities with the USGS Alaska Climate Science Center and NOAA Climate Service to ensure no duplication of effort
- Important to entrain relevant NGO's at the science level

C. Other Comments and Suggestions? Discussion was opened for any other comments or suggestions:

- The process of science and research can take a long time, but decision-makers are under pressure to make decisions immediately and in the short term – LCC should consider ways to provide information that can facilitate decisions in the near-term.

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Margaret Petersen
2. Niels Dau
3. Dirk Derksen (USGS)
4. Tammy Muller
5. Geoffrey Lloyd
6. Audrey Bohl (USFWS)
7. Didem Ikis (Pennsylvania State University)
8. Tyrone Donnelly (USGS)
9. Franz Muller (USFWS)
10. Ken Peterson
11. Bruce Casler (USFWS)
12. Nancy Hoffman (USFWS)
13. Haim Wenger
14. Jorge Lopez

15. Spencer Berg (USFWS)

16. Gary Ferguson

Karen Murphy (Western AK LCC Coordinator)

Susan Fox (ARCUS, Facilitation)

Helen Wiggins (ARCUS, Facilitation)

Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)
King Salmon Meeting
Wednesday, 13 October 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of document)

II. Western AK LCC Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion

A. What Are Your Observations of Landscape or Species Changes? Participants were asked to discuss any changes they have observed in the landscape or wildlife:

- Coastal Erosion – Several villages in Western AK are seeing significant changes from coastal erosion
- Vegetation Change
 - Seeing spruce beetle kills and unhealthy trees. Based on tree-ring analysis, die-offs have happened in the past but it seems to be happening more frequently.
 - Recently had a severe caterpillar outbreak on willow and alder, which had not been seen before
 - Elders in local villages have reported more alder growth
- Drying/lower water level of ponds – Area villages reported decreasing lake levels; when flying over the peninsula, we see a lot of lakes that have dried recently
- Wildlife
 - Local caribou herd declined significantly about 10 years ago
 - Area villages have also reported disappearing wildlife and new bird species (e.g., great blue heron)

B. What are Important Data, Science, and/or Management Needs?

- Better understanding of climate patterns at the local and regional level (e.g., are recent colder summers part of a natural cycle, etc.?)
- Need to better understand possible increase in spruce populations, as this will affect bird species and habitat availability
- Need data/maps on lake levels, such as including digitized lake boundaries, so that lake change can be monitored
- Habitat change is one of the most critical issues that requires data and modeling efforts (including at a very fine scale such as nutritional value of forage, etc.); need habitat species models; the LCC could provide an opportunity for collaboration since habitat crosses organizational and geographic boundaries
- Need baseline data on plant pests

- Need good planning and coordination for monitoring protocols, including collaboration on where to place monitoring and data collection to best address management issues
- Need for increased science and data management collaboration between agencies, including U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), National Park Service (NPS), Alaska Department of Fish and Game, and others
- Hydrological data/monitoring needed; very few gauging stations currently exist in the area
- Pressing need for geospatial/geographic data/GIS databases in USFWS refuges. NPS is much further along in this regard. Also overall need for better network connectivity and capability
- Important value the LCC could provide is to leverage across programs within agencies, leverage between agencies, and augment existing activities

C. Relevant Contacts, Groups, or Planning Documents:

- Lake data - Eric Taylor (FWS) was working with a graduate student at UAF who had started working on digitizing lakes (Joel Reynolds, LCC Science Coordinator, to follow-up)
- ABR, Inc. – might have paired historical photos to show landscape changes
- Dick Russell – long-term local King Salmon resident (retired AK Dept. of Fish & Game) has logged his landscape and wildlife observations over a long period of time and is trying to transfer them to a database
- National Park Service coastal marine monitoring protocols might be relevant
- There is a group forming focused on eelgrass that involves a lot of different experts, including agencies and academic community (David Ward is contact)
- Bristol Bay Regional Vision group: www.bristolbayvision.org
- Relevant Native Corporations and Regional Advisory Councils (RACs)
- Ugashik Watershed Committee (citizen science group)
- Chignik Regional Aquaculture Association has commercial fish catch statistics
- Boreal Partners in Flight:
<http://alaska.usgs.gov/science/biology/bpif/index.php/bpif.html>
- Permafrost experts – Torre Jorgenson (ABR, Inc.), and Vladimir Romanovsky (UAF)
- U.S. Climate Reference Network: <http://www.ncdc.noaa.gov/crn/>
- Bristol Bay Native Association (BBNA): <http://www.bbna.com/>
- USFWS and USGS have developed conceptual ecoregional models through workshops; these can be used as a start for LCC conceptual models leading into the 2011 State of the Science Workshop

- Document - USFWS "Revised Comprehensive Conservation Plan and Environmental Impact Statement", 2005. NPS has similar document – General Management Plan (GMP) and Land Protection Plans.
- Document - The Nature Conservancy, "Alaska Peninsula and Bristol Bay Basin Ecoregions"
- Document - AK Dept. of Fish and Game, "Bristol Bay Critical Habitat Areas," 2010
- Document - Bureau of Land Management (BLM), Dec 2007, "Bay Proposed Resource Management Plan and Final Environment Impact Statement"

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Orville Lind, USFWS
2. Susan Savage, USFWS
3. Julie Pinnix, USFWS
4. Bill Schaff, USFWS
5. Michael Brady, USFWS
6. Marla Greanya, USFWS
7. Amanda Boshers, USFWS
8. Stacey Pecen, USFWS
9. Ron Britton, USFWS
10. Troy Hamon, NPS
11. Carissa Turner, NPS
12. [1-2 others dropped in briefly]

Karen Murphy, Western AK LCC Coordinator
 Joel Reynolds, Western AK LCC Science Coordinator
 Susan Fox, ARCUS
 Helen Wiggins, ARCUS

Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)
Dillingham Meeting
Thursday, 14 October 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK LCC Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western Ak LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion

A. What Are Your Observations of Landscape or Species Changes?

- *Erosion* – Coastal erosion is one of the largest concerns in the area
- *Fish and Wildlife*
 - Loss of caribou over the past decade, which is an important subsistence resource
 - Wildlife health - have some reports of growths in caribou, lesions on whitefish
 - Birds - biologist found a common snipe that had overwintered this past year, which was the first record of that in the state; reports of new bird species (e.g., possible stellar sea eagle sighting, different kind of seagull); increase in ravens (possibly due to more human development and waste); migration pattern this past year started early in spring and ended late
 - Increase in bear populations recently - seeing sows with four cubs (could be due to warm winter last year)
 - Reports of different kinds of moths, butterflies, and bees
 - Pike is expanding their range
 - Moose seem to be expanding west along with the expansion of spruce
- *Vegetation Changes*
 - Increasing shrub growth (alder and willow) in formerly tundra areas is one of the most obvious landscape change – essentially a change from 'caribou habitat' to more 'moose habitat'
 - More spruce and spruce range is expanding west
 - Generally a longer growing season
 - Eelgrass beds experiences more siltation in some areas
 - Around Katmai, saw a leaf miner outbreak, which had not been seen before
 - Some vegetation seems to be growing in different forms (e.g., fireweed growing as bushier structure), and also seeing different kinds of plants

- *Other*
 - Has been windier in recent years
 - Have seen more extreme weather
 - Less ice on rivers
 - Glaciers retreating – the Refuge documented that 10% of glaciers in the Wood River Mountains were lost since the 1970's
 - Less snow recently and it seems to be drier (does not pack down), but one participant said that his grandmother described times with no snow when she was young
 - Socioeconomic changes also important to consider (development, changes in technology, etc.)
 - A water temperature monitoring program is actually showing cooling of some stream water temperatures over the last 10 years

B. What are Important Data, Science, Management, or Partnership Needs?

- Mapping of coastline to monitor coastal erosion – periodic surveys, shoreline/erosion time-series mapping is needed
- Several suggestions that LCC be structured to provide a 'clearinghouse' for relevant scientific data, information on other efforts, and networking tools between groups and also local communities
- Need a coordinated 'umbrella' structure to capture and disseminate climate change information
- There is a need to engage K-12 students and encourage science careers (e.g., through internships or other opportunities)
- Need to provide information that is easily understood by the public and local communities so it can be used to make local decisions (e.g., tools to provide cost/benefit analysis for local management decisions)
- There currently is not enough money or manpower to address all of the science or management needs, so LCC should help leverage and coordinate existing resources and fill in remaining gaps
- Formal inclusion of indigenous knowledge and local communities is needed; this has been done successfully with the Bering Sea Integrated Ecosystem Research Program (BSIERP: <http://bsierp.nprb.org/>)
- Bristol Bay Regional Vision is a relevant effort (<http://www.bristolbayvision.org/>)
- Need to be able to understand weather and current climate patterns in the larger context of climate change
- There was a set of meetings about five years ago where conservation groups and tribes discussed similar information and science needs – LCC should incorporate the results of those discussions (Norman Anderson, BBNA, can help provide information)
- An online resource would be useful, with information that everyone can access
- More satellite imagery is needed to help quantify terrestrial and aquatic habitats
- More hydrological monitoring stations as well as better sharing of existing data is needed

- In addition to the regional level (i.e. 'western Alaska'), also need more local data
- Relevant publication: Traditional Ecological Knowledge of 20th-Century Ecosystems and Fish Population in the Kuskokwim Bay Region. Robbin LaVine, Bristol Bay Native Association, Mark Lisac, USFWS, Phillipa Coiley-Kenner, AK Dept. of Fish and Game. Final Report, Fisheries Resources Monitoring Program, FIS 04-35

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Jody Seitz, City of Dillingham
2. Celeste Novak, BB CSRA
3. Michael Swaim, Togiak NWR
4. Lorraine King, Ekwok Village Council
5. Mark Lisac, Togiak NWR
6. Jon Dyasuk, Togiak NWR
7. Ted Krieg, Subsistence Division, Ak Dept. of Fish and Game
8. Norm Anderson, BBNA
9. Duncan Nielsen, Togiak NWR
10. Jason Dye, Sport Fish, AK Dept Fish and Game
11. Jim Woolington, Wildlife Conservation, AK Dept Fish and Game
12. Paul Liedberg, Togiak NWR
13. Jim Loiland, NRCS
14. Tevis Underwood, Togiak NWR
15. Frank Woods, BBNA
16. Michele Masley, Bristol Bay Campus

Karen Murphy, Western AK LCC Coordinator
 Susan Fox, ARCUS
 Helen Wiggins, ARCUS

**Western AK and Arctic Landscape Conservation Cooperatives (LCC)
Joint Anchorage Meeting
Tuesday, 19 October 2010**

Summary Notes

I. Introductions

(Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see list of participants at end of notes)

II. Joint Western AK and Arctic Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Presentation

A PowerPoint presentation by LCC staff provided an overview of the LCC effort and a brief update on the status of the Western AK LCC and the Arctic LCC.

- The Western Alaska LCC overview slides were presented by Karen Murphy, Western LCC Coordinator
- The Arctic LCC overview slides were presented by Greg Balogh, Arctic LCC Coordinator

III. General Discussion on Landscape Conservation Cooperatives (LCCs) - Meeting participants were invited to ask general questions about the LCC efforts.

Overall Governance, Budget, and Structural Issues – Several questions arose on the overall structure and processes of the LCCs:

- A participant requested clarification of the LCC decision-making process: Greg Balogh addressed this question since the Arctic LCC has a charter (while the Western AK LCC has not been officially formed yet):
 - The LCC Steering Committee steers the LCC direction, while the LCC staff have some latitude in decision-making, as granted by the Steering Committee. In general, the LCC staff serves the Steering Committee, but without being staff "of" the Steering Committee. LCC staff draw on collective wishes of the Steering Committee. Big decisions of the LCC are supposed to be made by consensus.
- Question on the absence of non-governmental organizations on the LCC Steering Committee.
 - LCC staff responded that the Steering Committee is now limited by the Federal Advisory Committee Act (FACA, 1972) and so is currently limited to "government-to-government" partnerships. However, the LCC is working on this issue in DC and exploring options so that non-governmental organizations could serve on the Steering Committee. For now, NGOs are included in the "partnerships-at-large" level and also can be represented within the LCC Technical Working Groups.

- Joel Reynolds, Western AK LCC Science Coordinator, noted that there is a national LCC meeting scheduled this fall in DC, where LCC procedures and structure will be addressed, so that Western and Arctic LCC staff can bring up these issues at the national level.
- Question asking for an overview of the LCC budget
 - *Response for the Arctic LCC (response by Greg Balogh):*
 - The Arctic LCC is funded at a \$2M base, with \$1M to use as seed money for science projects and \$1M for salaries/travel/administrative costs.
 - The vision is that the LCCs will be able to award project seed money to other entities – university researchers, other agencies, NGO science staff, etc.
 - The LCCs will be working on the details as far as how funding calls will be structured.
 - In addition, part of the vision of the LCC is that ideas will bubble-up above the LCC level into each agency, for example, through the Alaska Climate Change Executive Roundtable (ACCER), where additional funding and resources could be leveraged.
 - Participation on an LCC Steering Group or Working Group does not prevent a partner from seeking LCC project funding.
 - *Response for the Western AK LCC (response by Karen Murphy):*
 - The Western AK LCC funding is not yet finalized, but they hope for a similar funding level to the Arctic LCC.
 - For the Western AK LCC, once they know if they have project funds, they will be looking for initial project ideas for the shorter-term, and then they will have a longer-term strategy once the LCC is in place and priorities are determined. These meetings, plus the science meeting in the spring, will help determine initial direction for the LCC.
- Question on the Distinction between "Deep" Versus "Applied" Science in LCC's
 - Greg Balogh - The LCCs could address both "basic" research and applied science, but in general the LCC would be more directed to applied science, while the Alaska Climate Science Center (CSC, led by USGS) will be addressing the "deep science" or basic research. However, basic science activities like filling in gaps in current monitoring/observing networks might be accomplished through LCCs. The LCCs and CSC will coordinate closely to ensure no duplication of effort.
- Question regarding LCC sustainability and long-term funding
 - LCC staff reported that the intent of LCCs is to be long-term and sustainable, though government funding is always "year by year."
 - A meeting participant noted that the government does not always have to work "year by year" and there are mechanisms to fund sustainable, multi-

year programs (such as Long Term Ecological Research Network sites (LTER), and so the LCC should get firm commitment on LCC as a long-term effort, which will help potential partners see the value in committing time or resources to LCCs.

- During the initial start-up years of the LCCs, projects that do not need multiple years of funding are preferred so as to not over-commit funding while LCC direction/priorities are being established. There is the potential for making multi-year commitments to address LCC priorities in the future.

Relation of LCC to Other Ongoing Efforts

- Several participants asked how the LCCs will avoid duplicating efforts of current agencies and groups. LCC staff recognized this concern and addressed the question with the following points:
 - The core vision of the LCCs is that they would build on or supplement existing efforts and partnerships, not duplicate work.
 - The LCCs will be managed to help leverage funds for the highest priority science needs.
 - LCC will also have staff that can help build and sustain collaborations.
 - There is not a lot of funding available for science in the Arctic and Alaska, even though there are a lot of science needs and gaps in the region, so LCC can help supplement that.
 - For example, environmental monitoring activities might be undertaken by various agencies and projects, but an LCC could pull these together through a database and/or tie individual projects in with larger agency activities.
- Several meeting participants emphasized the need for the LCCs to become aware of, and build on, already existing or developing efforts or documents, including those efforts that have already identified various research priorities. LCC staff agreed and these meetings are one of the first steps in that process.
- Question to LCC staff regarding connections with international partners
 - For Arctic LCC, have had initial connections with Canada so far, but will do this more.
 - For Western AK LCC, they have talked with Canada Wildlife Service and Environment Canada – both are interested in engaging; have not yet connected with Russia. And there are also circumpolar groups that will need to engage with.
 - Participant suggestion to talk with Arctic Council and AMAP for Arctic LCC
- One participant noted that public health and how climate change will affect disease is an important landscape issue that the LCCs could consider.

IV. Discussion on the Arctic LCC Specifically

- Greg Balogh presented a PowerPoint focused on the Arctic LCC, including information on the Arctic LCC Steering Committee and "Partnerships at Large," staffing, funded projects, and the Technical Working Groups.

General Arctic LCC Questions

- Question on the balance in the Arctic LCC between terrestrial and marine focus
 - Terrestrial science was the initial focus for Arctic LCC's first set of projects. The LCC is currently urging NOAA to get as active as possible in the LCC so that the LCC can include more of the marine realm (marine mammals, sea birds, etc.). Overall, the LCC plans to become more even between marine and terrestrial science, and they also need to talk with those involved with White House's National Ocean Council (NOC) and Coastal and Marine Spatial Planning efforts.
 - Joel Reynolds (Western AK LCC Science Coordinator) – The Western AK LCC also has these issues in mind, and have spoken with the Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS) staff to ensure the Western AK LCC builds on AOOS efforts, especially in the data management/data discovery realm.
- Questions on the LCC funded projects
 - Question on where more information on 2010 funded projects can be found:
 - The LCC will be putting more information on the website, and are also working on fact sheets about projects that will be distributed and posted on the website.
 - Question on whether the Steering Committee members, when they approved the research projects, ensured they did not overlap existing efforts:
 - In the initial round of 2010 projects, LCC staff (Philip Martin, Science Coordinator) guided the selection of projects based on the LCC WildREACH workshop report and other documents. For the selection of 2010 projects, they did not have time for a formal planning or decision process, but in the future, projects will be determined based on agreed-upon priorities.
 - Greg directed additional questions on the currently funded projects to Philip Martin, Arctic LCC Science Coordinator (philip_martin@fws.gov)

Discussion on Technical Working Groups

- Greg emphasized that there are opportunities for meeting participants to participate in any of the Technical Working Groups (currently have five: Geospatial Data, Hydrology, Permafrost, Coastal Processes, and Climate and Downscaled Modeling) and none of the membership is set.
- Question on how the topics for the Technical Working Groups were chosen.
 - They were chosen based on the WildREACH report and NSSI documents, with a focus on physical processes, rather than species-driven.
- Question on how the membership of the Technical Working Groups are formed
 - The Steering Committee approves the creation of a Working Group, but does not determine the membership.
 - So far, Philip Martin has led initial discussions for Working Group membership and is reaching into the various science communities to find members with relevant expertise, asking for 40–60 hours/year commitment from members.
 - The Technical Working Groups are just being formed now and nothing is set or final. So far, the geospatial group is the only group that has met (they have met once).
- Meeting participants discussed suggestions for other or additional Technical Working Groups, including:
 - Human/community impacts
 - Wildlife, and/or a clearer avenue for wildlife biologists to participate in the Working Groups and to ensure priorities are related to wildlife management needs
 - Habitat connectivity
 - Species of Interest
 - Project tracking (perhaps as sub-group under the Geospatial Working Group)
 - Marine issues (either as separate group or sub-group)
 - Long-term monitoring
 - Vegetation (might include rare species, vegetation/cover type mapping, habitat, etc.)
 - Subsistence
- Other suggestions from meeting participants relevant to the working groups included:
 - LCC could consider targeting Working Groups at a broader level (from which more specific projects could be developed), with different areas of disciplinary expertise within each group.
 - LCC should look to statewide groups for efforts already in place (e.g., invasive species statewide group).

- LCC should think more about communication and interaction among the Working Groups as well as between the Working Groups and other efforts, as the science and management issues are cross-cutting and do not have defined disciplinary or geographic boundaries.
 - LCCs might want to think about Working Group topics that are broad enough to be the same across the Alaska LCCs, for consistency.
 - Need some type of coordinated effort for downscaling/modeling work.
 - The Steering Committee needs to decide on a process for integrating non-LCC efforts into the LCC Working Groups, to avoid duplication of work.
- Question on how LCC science staff positions (geospatial specialist, data manager, hydrologist, data modeler) will fit into the Working Groups:
 - The LCC geospatial specialist recently hired is heading up Geospatial Working Group. But there will not be an LCC science staff person to lead each Working Group – this is where the LCC will need various partners to help lead Working Groups.

Existing Efforts and Potential Partnerships

- Several participants asked for clarification on the relationship between the North Slope Science Initiative (NSSI) and the Arctic LCC. LCC staff addressed the question with the following points:
 - The Arctic LCC has a unique situation because the NSSI is in place and has already done a lot of work. The LCC and NSSI have been discussing how to work together and leverage funding.
 - The NSSI is not a voting presence on the Arctic LCC Steering Committee, but their Executive Director regularly attends Steering Committee meetings. The NSSI and the LCC have a lot of overlap in membership, and the LCC will hopefully be adding the North Slope Borough to the Steering Committee in the future (a seat awaits them).
 - One difference to note between the NSSI and the LCC is that the geographic focus of the NSSI is the North Slope, while the LCC is broader, including marine waters within the exclusive economic zone (EEZ). Also, the LCC is being organized within a national framework of LCCs, with eventual goal that the science done within each LCC can be scaled up to a national level. For the LCCs, there will be a national framework for data integration, monitoring protocols, etc.
 - Several participants discussed an effort by NSSI to develop a project-tracking database to share information on research projects being conducted in arctic Alaska, and suggested that this might be a good effort for the LCC to link to and/or build on. The National Science Foundation also has funded a project-tracking mapping database. The Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS) is also undertaking a project database. Participants familiar with these efforts

stressed that project-tracking databases require a lot of coordination and staff time.

- A meeting participant noted that the NSSI is working on a paper on the history of science on the North Slope, as well as a paper that synthesizes research issues and needs on the North Slope (e.g., need for development of future scenarios, need for long-term monitoring); these NSSI documents could be drawn on in the LCC effort.
- Geographic Information Network of Alaska (GINA; <http://www.gina.alaska.edu/>) provides a framework for linking to geospatial data.
- There are major long-term issues of developing data discovery and access tools for the arctic that should be resolved.
- There are already statewide groups focused on various topical issues, for example the Alaska Invasive Species Working Group (<http://www.uaf.edu/ces/aiswg/>), and the LCC should contact and link to these.
- A non-governmental resource that could be useful is the Climate Adaptation Knowledge Exchange (CAKE; <http://www.cakex.org/>), which is building a shared knowledge base for managing natural systems in the face of rapid climate change.
- It is important for the LCC to get away from the restrictions of Federal Advisory Committee Act (FACA) and only having government agencies on the LCC Steering Committee.
- Participant question on tribal consultation. LCC staff responded that they are seeking to involve tribes and other native organizations, and also hope to get the North Slope Borough participating in the Steering Committee.
- LCC staff emphasized that the LCC can help "connect the dots" between existing activities and communicate between groups; the LCC does not want to re-invent any efforts.
- LCC staff would like to help build a process or tools that link together relevant efforts and projects, whether or not they are funded through the LCC - perhaps a web resource.

Communications – Participants shared several ideas for LCC communications and networking activities:

- Despite all the meetings various groups hold, there is still a gap for place-based meetings focused on the North Slope. It would be useful to be able to meet regularly about regional issues (perhaps annually, similar to the Alaska Marine Science Symposium).

- The LCC might consider a focus on what local communities and resources managers need to know and the issues they face.
- LCC should consider working on the agency 'branding' of LCCs – now it appears to be a USFWS effort, not interagency. For example, for LCC meetings, might avoid holding them primarily in FWS buildings.
- Question on whether the Arctic LCC has a communication plan
 - The LCC does not have an external communication plan yet, but are thinking about these issues and potential activities – such as an annual conference or other ways people can get information and participate.

Measures of Success – Participant asked the LCC staff how they will measure success of the LCCs

- LCC staff responded that one measure of success will be forming partnerships, increasing communication between groups, and networking. The other measure of success would be if activities generated through the LCC informed on-the-ground conservation goals. The nationwide LCC network is now discussing the metrics of success, as well.
- One participant noted that one of the most exciting possibilities of the LCC is the potential for the LCC to provide a contact or clearinghouse that could answer questions from communities on landscape science, climate change data, etc.
 - LCC staff responded that they could envision the LCC providing that role, but also envision two-way communications, so that the community and scientists would *contribute to* the LCC clearinghouse as well as look to the LCC for information.

Other Questions

- Question on whether there would be cooperation between the AK LCCs in staffing, as there should be coordination between the LCCs to avoid duplication
 - The LCCs are in the process of discussing this issue.
- Question on what will happen to LCCs if there is a change in the White House administration, as there is concern and people are reluctant to get involved for fear that the LCCs will not be a long-term activity
 - The LCCs will be talking about this at a national and agency level, and hope that the LCC becomes "institutionalized" as a branch of Department of Interior.

Participant List

Name	Organization
1. Mike Brubaker	Ak Native Tribal Health Consortium
2. Caryn Rea	Conoco Phillips
3. Karla Dutton	Defenders of Wildlife
4. Michael Shephard	NPS
5. Cheryl Rosa	USARC
6. John Payne	North Slope Science Initiative (NSSI)
7. Wendy Loya	The Wilderness Society
8. Dee Williams	BOEMRE
9. Nils Warnick	Audubon Alaska
10. Steve Zack	Wildlife Conservation Society
11. Dave Howell	BLM
12. Steph McAfee	The Wilderness Society
13. Mike Daigneault	AK Dept. Fish and Game
14. Joel Clemant	Wilburforce Foundation
15. Andrew Hartsig	Ocean Conservancy
16. Keith Boggs	AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA
17. Monica McTeague	AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA
18. Eric F. Myers	Audubon Alaska
19. Bill Streever	BP
20. Mark Shasby	USGS
21. Cindi Jacobson	USFWS
22. Kristin (Holzinger) K'eit	BIA
23. June McAfee	Calista Corp.
24. Evie Witten	The Nature Conservancy
25. Diane Sanzone	BP
26. Crystal Leonetti	USFWS
Greg Balogh	Arctic LCC Coordinator
Karen Murphy	Western AK LCC Coordinator
Joel Reynolds	Western AK LCC Science Coordinator
Susan Fox	ARCUS, Facilitation
Helen Wiggins	ARCUS, Facilitation

Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)
Kodiak Meeting
Tuesday, 26 October 2010

Summary Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK LCC Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion

A. General Questions About the LCC - Participants were invited to ask questions on any aspect of the LCC:

- Question on whether the geographic boundaries of the different AK LCCs are fixed:
 - They are not fixed, especially since the Western Alaska region is so diverse; there have been some discussions on whether Kodiak would fit better with the interior LCC. Ultimately, the different LCCs could coordinate together on issues that cross LCC boundaries. For example, brown bear management issues could be coordinated across all LCCs with brown bear populations.

- Question on what process is being used in the community meetings to identify local priorities:
 - The community meetings are not meant as a formal prioritization process; at this early stage the LCC staff are just gathering ideas, finding contacts, and sharing information.
 - A meeting participant noted that this meeting has primarily agency representatives, so would not necessarily represent perspectives of other Kodiak-based organizations, native associations, etc.

- Question to clarify the organizational structure of LCC and if the LCC will be sending people out to do field work:
 - The LCC will not be sending or staffing field teams out to do work in the refuges, etc. though they may sponsor teams to collect needed data or expand scope of existing efforts. Implementation of conservation lies with the agency that has authority for that action. The more likely role of LCC staff would be in activities such as data assimilation and processing, climate scenarios, database development, monitoring protocols, etc.
 - The LCC will primarily be structured to leverage existing activities, funding, and staffing in various agencies, and to fill in gaps and coordinate as needed.

- Question on level of LCC funding:
 - For the Western AK LCC, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service anticipates funding for core LCC staff through the Department of Interior (the funding structure is different for the different LCCs). The Western AK LCC will likely have a base annual funding of \$2M, with \$1M of that to fund project activities.
 - The mechanism for Western AK LCC calls for project proposals has not yet been determined, but for the first 1-2 years the project selection process will probably be done by the LCC Steering Committee, rather than a formal Request for Proposals as a formal process is developed.
 - If the Western AK LCC receives funding for 2011 projects, they will work through the Steering Committee to identify projects. The initial focus will be on short-term projects (that do not require funding in future years) that are clearly tied to management decisions. For example, a monitoring activity or station could be added to fill in a critical gap to an existing monitoring program, at very little cost.
 - After the Western AK LCC State of the Science Meeting in spring 2011, the LCC will identify Technical Working Groups, which will explore where the specific science needs are, recommend priorities for LCC projects, and help frame future Requests for Proposals.

- Question on how the LCC will organize or approach the scientific topics:
 - With the LCC State of the Science workshop, will start with a focus on ecological *processes* and examine how processes (and changes in processes) affect species and issues of management concern.

- Question on how the LCC Steering Committee is comprised:
 - There is currently an interim Steering Committee comprised of state and federal agency representatives.
 - In the Alaska LCCs, because the state has the Alaska Climate Change Executive Roundtable (ACCER) with high-level agency representatives, the Alaska LCC Steering Committees have more "on the ground" representatives (refuge managers, park superintendants, etc.).
 - It is up to each agency on the Steering Committee to appoint their Steering Committee representatives and to determine their own rotation schedule. At this time there are two representatives allowed per agency.
 - Currently, non-government entities cannot serve on the Steering Committee (due to Federal Advisory Committee Act rules), but representatives of these entities can serve on the Technical Working Groups, and are encouraged to do so. These Technical Working Groups are extremely important in providing recommendations for science foci and priorities.

- Question on whether the LCC will develop Memoranda of Understanding/Agreement to transfer funds between agencies:
 - The LCCs at the national level are discussing this, as it is a very important issue, and it can be very expensive to transfer funds between agencies due to overhead costs.
 - In addition, the vision for the LCCs is that federal and state agencies also contribute funds at the agency-budget level, in addition to the funding specific to the LCC budget.
- A meeting participant suggested that the Migratory Bird Joint Ventures program (see: <http://www.fws.gov/birdhabitat/jointventures/index.shtm>) would be a good model for the LCC, as it has an open, transparent process and has clear priorities for project funding. The Joint Venture model was instrumental in setting up the national LCC concept.

B. What are Important Data, Science, and/or Management Needs? Participants were invited to discuss their perspectives on critical science needs:

- Monitoring is one of the most critical needs (weather, hydrological, ocean temperatures, etc.); there is a dire lack of baseline information. Also, the Kodiak Archipelago is a very diverse area, so many sites are needed to capture the ecosystem variability.
- The ocean-land interface (e.g., shoreline, intertidal, estuary zones) is important to understanding linkages between terrestrial and marine systems and is also important for key species such as salmon.
- "Ecosystem indicators" (which are being developed in the marine science realm) might be useful to help define and assess ecosystem condition.
- Information on salmon is important for management decisions.
- Overall hydrological information is needed, including storage capacity and flow, water budget predictions.
- Eelgrass beds are critical habitat, but very little research has been done on eelgrass.
- Information on human impacts and development is needed, especially on Kodiak.
- A big challenge and need is integration across the region on common science needs and management concerns, and to identify priorities that are common across the region, keeping in mind that the science issues and ecosystems cross geographic and LCC boundaries.

- One of the biggest benefits the LCC could provide is to educate everyone on what activities and science is being done on climate science in the region and to foster collaboration; this is a big task in and of itself.

C. What Are Your Observations of Landscape or Species Changes? Participants were asked to discuss any changes they have observed in the landscape or wildlife:

- More invasive plants (not sure of driver for this, whether it is climate-related and/or human activity)
- Concern about introduced bison and other introduced mammals in the Kodiak area, and the effects on native flora and biological diversity.
- Another human activity of concern is spruce forest cutting and introduction of different coniferous tree species for economic/market reasons.

D. Suggestions for Other Groups and Potential Partners? Participants suggested other groups or efforts relevant to LCC discussions and potential partnerships:

- Gulf Ecosystem Monitoring program (see: http://www.nap.edu/catalog.php?record_id=10469) – this initiative was never fully implemented, but ideas are relevant, and some of the work was implemented through the Bering Sea Integrated Ecosystem Research Program (BSIERP; <http://bsierp.nprb.org/index.html>).
- NOAA activities, especially regarding work on salmon, shoreline mapping, and other issues with terrestrial linkages; as well as capabilities to process water monitoring samples.
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service has started land cover/remote sensing mapping that would help provide baseline information, and there is cooperation with the Natural Resources Conservation Service (<http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/>) to conduct soil surveys.
- Critical at this stage to cooperate with Canada and Russia, including discussion of data and monitoring protocols. The LCC could link into work already done with the National Park Service's Shared Berengian Heritage Program (<http://www.nps.gov/akso/beringia/index.cfm>), the Arctic Council's Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) program (http://arctic-council.org/working_group/caff), and the Northern Forum (<http://www.northernforum.org/>).
- In 2010, the U.S. Geological Survey Alaska Science Center and Kodiak National Wildlife Refuge held a workshop on "Integrated Anticipation and Accommodation of Climate-

Change Effects in the Karluk River Watershed," which identified research needs; the results of this workshop should feed into LCC discussions.

- Other relevant groups and efforts include the US Fish and Wildlife Service Office of Subsistence Management (<http://alaska.fws.gov/asm/osm.cfml>), the Kodiak Area Native Association (KANA; <http://www.kanaweb.org/>), the U.S. Coast Guard, and the Gulf of Alaska Integrated Ecosystem Research Program (GOA-IERP; <http://goaierp.nprb.org/>).

Notes Addendum: Karen Murphy met with several local agency representatives in the morning before the open meeting. The following issues were discussed:

- The role of human dimensions/sociology in the LCCs - "cultural resources" are included in the components to be addressed by the LCC within a landscape context. How broad of a definition of "cultural resources" the LCC will use is still to be decided, though there will clearly be a tie through subsistence, indigenous knowledge, and perhaps to climate change effects on cultural sites.
- There are opportunities to bring resource managers together throughout the southern half of the LCC (which includes 4 refuges and 3 national parks) on their seabird monitoring protocols. There is early dialog on this between U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and National Park Service; the LCC could provide assistance in refining protocols, etc. Similarly, bald eagle surveys are conducted differently between neighboring refuges. The different surveys provide different information to Migratory Bird Management to meet bald eagle objectives, but it is unclear if it would be more effective to adopt one approach across the LCC.

V. Meeting Participants

1. Robert Foy, NOAA-NMFS
2. Matt Nemeth, AK Department of Fish and Game-commercial fisheries
3. Kent Sundseth, USFWS-Kodiak National Wildlife Refuge
4. Gary_Wheeler, USFWS-Kodiak National Wildlife Refuge
5. G. Kevin VanHatten, Jr., USFWS-Kodiak National Wildlife Refuge
6. McCrea Cobb, USFWS- Kodiak
7. Michelle LeBeau, Kodiak Soil and Water Conservation District
8. Stacy Studebaker, Kodiak Audubon
9. Bill Pyle, USFWS-Kodiak National Wildlife Refuge
10. Larry Van Daele, Ak Department of Fish and Game – Wildlife

Karen Murphy, Western AK LCC Coordinator; Susan Fox, ARCUS, Meeting Facilitation;
Helen Wiggins, ARCUS, Meeting Facilitation

**Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)
Bethel Meeting**

Tuesday, 2 November 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Western AK LCC Presentation (Paul Krabacher, LCC Steering Committee, Bureau of Land Management)

II. Open Discussion – The meeting was opened for questions and discussion on the LCC.

A. General Questions About the LCC

- Question on whether there will be funding competition between LCC and the USGS Alaska Climate Science Center (CSC)?
 - No, the LCC and CSC will be complementary; the CSC's mission is to undertake science that supports management needs and LCC priorities. The CSCs will be more focused on 'deep science', while the LCC focus will be on 'applied science.'
- Question on overall structure and LCC organizational chart
 - There is currently an interim Steering Committee; a charter has not yet been developed. The LCC structure includes the Alaska Climate Change Executive Roundtable (ACCER) with high-level agency representatives, then the LCC Steering Committee, and as-needed Working Groups will be formed to provide recommendations to the Steering Committee.
- Question on types of activities the LCC might perform, such as acting as a central data clearinghouse or portal, leveraging funds for science, or actually funding projects?
 - All of the above could be possible roles of the LCC; the LCC Steering Committee and staff are now in the process of defining early roles for the LCC.

B. Relevant Existing Efforts, Research, or Groups

- The Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge has recently launched several projects. The major effort is to develop baseline data so that habitat change (e.g., drying wetlands) can be monitored. The baseline datasets include a LIDAR survey over a 100-square mile area, photogrammetric work, and IKONOS imagery for a wider region. Development of the baseline data will continue next year, then the refuge plans on repeating field monitoring every 3-5 years, with a new photogrammetric baseline dataset every 20 years. The refuge has also started a coastal processes monitoring project, which includes meteorological stations, USGS sea level stations, frost tubes/monitoring, and mapping activities. In addition, the refuge has a reference site for waterfowl population

monitoring, a salmon project to examine stream conditions, and moose exclusion surveys to assess affect of moose grazing on vegetation.

- The refuge developed a document that prioritized refuge science needs entitled: "Yukon Delta National Wildlife Refuge: 2008 Biological Review." Thomas Doolittle, Supervisory Wildlife Biologist. May 25, 2009. [Note: Tom Doolittle provided a PDF of the report].
- Other USFWS refuges have also done various science prioritization exercises (including the Izembek and Kodiak refuges).
- Relevant groups for science in this region include: Ducks Unlimited (<http://www.ducks.org/alaska>), the Alaska SeaLife Center (<http://www.alaskasealife.org/>), Native Corporations and Village Councils (could consider videoconferencing to reach area villages), and Alaska Department of Fish and Game (<http://www.adfg.state.ak.us/>). It was noted that there is a specific need for improved collaboration between federal and state agencies.

C. Important Science or Data Needs

- A major data gap for the refuge is a baseline inventory and monitoring of species and habitat. Currently, the majority of observations on landscape or species changes are anecdotal (e.g., increasing moose, increasing shrubs), so there is a need for baseline data and monitoring to detect changes, as well as information on how species may or may not be adapting to changing conditions.
- Also need to build and improve monitoring partnerships across agencies and organizations.
- Data on contaminants in fish and marine mammals is needed (e.g., beluga is an important subsistence species for coastal communities).
- Examples of specific data gaps include data on eelgrass, berries and terrestrial/aquatic insects (wildlife food sources), and understanding possible effects of sea level rise on salinization of freshwater habitats.
- It is important to consider other landscape changes in addition to climate change, such as development/population growth, contaminants, and ocean acidification.

D. Overall Suggestions for LCC Planning and Implementation

- One of the most critical issues for the LCC is to ensure it has long-term funding.
- LCC could consider producing a very simple, short, easy-to-read brochure geared to upper-level management and policy-makers to entrain broad support. If possible, this document would highlight where the LCC was able to leverage funds (e.g., LCC used \$X

project seed money and leveraged an additional \$X from various agencies and organizations for a specific management concern). It will be important for the LCC to clearly communicate how LCC science is in support of management issues, not just 'science for science's sake'.

- Another useful product would be an annual publication/newsletter that provides information on LCC progress, funded projects, etc.
- Outreach to the public is extremely important; the LCC should communicate on LCC science and how it is relevant to people's lives. The public is where ultimate buy-in and support lies.
- LCC could provide some type of network of experts, so when an agency or organization is lacking in a particular expertise (e.g., climate change, habitat modeling), they can reach into the LCC to fill gaps in expertise.
- A successful LCC would help resource managers provide information to local residents on changes and opportunities in subsistence resources, as well as help resource managers determine what species they should focus on for science and management efforts.
- A valuable role of the LCC would be to improve collaboration and cooperation between different refuges, agencies, and other organizations, with a focus on landscape-level science that informs resource management decisions. There are many barriers to intra- and inter-organizational collaboration and the LCC could help overcome those barriers. For example, the LCC could fund an 'umbrella' project and entrain relevant agencies to contribute.

III. Meeting Participants

1. Charisa Morris, USFWS
2. Thomas Doolittle, USFWS
3. Melissa Gabrielson, USFWS
4. Kristine Sowl, USFWS

- Paul Krabacher, BLM (Representing LCC Steering Committee and the BLM Rapid Ecoregional Assessment)
- Keith Boggs, AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA (Contractor for BLM Rapid Ecoregional Assessment)
- Susan Fox (ARCUS, Facilitation)
- Helen Wiggins (ARCUS, Facilitation)

Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)

Fairbanks Meeting

Thursday, 4 November 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Margaret King, Independent Consultant; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Presentation (Paul Krabacher, LCC Steering Committee Member; presentation included a brief overview of the Bureau of Land Management's [BLM] Rapid Ecological Assessment [REA] process)

III. Open Discussion – The meeting was opened for questions and discussion on the LCC

A. Participant Ideas on Science Needs, Data Gaps, or Landscape Management Issues Relevant to the LCC

- Need improved understanding on how hydrological changes may affect fish habitat and local water resources, and understanding recent changes in fish runs.
- More permafrost monitoring is needed as well as understanding of how changes in permafrost may affect hydrology, coastal erosion, vegetation patterns, and infrastructure. Permafrost science community is relatively small; an entity like the LCC could help build that science community.
- Need better information on fire frequency and severity; there is some evidence of changes, but the causes are not clear.
- Need social science data on patterns of resource use, including subsistence use, recreational use, and changes in accessibility (e.g., drying land allows travel to areas that were previously inaccessible).
- Need to understand how climate change will affect distribution and habitat of rare plants and animals, and invasive species.
- Need to better understand relative patterns of interannual variability relative to climate-induced changes in aquatic resources.
- Pursuing a general understanding of how the landscape will change in the next 10-20 years is a science need that is relevant to many different agencies and groups.
- Monitoring should be designed as complementary baseline studies rather than independent studies. Also, monitoring studies should be designed to take into account

local variability (e.g., patterns of climate change might be fairly consistent throughout a region, but patterns of permafrost changes are not).

- There is a need for a coordinated or centralized resource for communicating about research activities and centralizing involvement of local residents in research – a place where interested parties can go for "one stop shopping" to learn about or coordinate science efforts.

B. Participant Suggestions for Relevant Ongoing Efforts, Programs, or Groups

- The Alaska Center for Climate Assessment and Policy (ACCAP; <http://ine.uaf.edu/accap/>), which is NOAA-funded, is interested in working together with all of the Alaska LCCs. There is a formal MOU between NOAA and the Department of Interior to coordinate activities. ACCAP focuses on issues of, and information for, human adaptation and response to climate change.
- Native Alaska involvement will be important for the LCC overall and for coordinating local observing activities. Most tribes have an environmental coordinator, but it is important to contact *all* tribal organizations/groups in any given region.
- The new Alaska NOAA Climate Service will be collaborating with the LCCs as well as the USGS Climate Science Center. The principal mission of the NOAA Climate Service is to provide climate tools and products that are useful for decision-makers.
- Collaboration between state and federal agencies is critical.
- The Alaska Natural Heritage Program (<http://aknhp.uaa.alaska.edu/>) offers synthesized data via the web on rare plant and animal species as well as and invasive species.
- It is not clear how the Alaska Department of Fish and Game would fit into the LCC, nor the relationship between the Bureau of Land Management's Rapid Ecological Assessment (REA) and the LCC.
 - Paul Krabacher replied that for the REA/LCC relationship, the REA is more of a *process* that will contribute to the LCC, while the LCC is more of a 'group.'
- The Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning (SNAP; <http://www.snap.uaf.edu/>) has been working with the Arctic LCC and is providing spatial data layers/datasets, which should come online spring 2011, possibly through the Geographic Information Network of Alaska (GINA).
- The Maniilaq Association and the Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium recently convened a two-day summit in Kotzebue to discuss how the changing climate will impact human health; this was a valuable meeting relevant to the LCC.

C. Other Questions or Issues

- Question on whether there will be a document similar to the WildREACH report (<http://www.arcus.org/alaskafws/>)
 - Paul Krabacher replied that yes, there will be a Western AK LCC planning document produced after the spring 2011 State of the Science workshop.
- Question on timeline of funding for the LCC
 - Paul Krabacher replied that funding is not yet allocated for Western AK LCC, but funding in FY2011 is likely.

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Sarah Trainor, Alaska Center for Climate Assessment and Policy (ACCAP) and Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning (SNAP)
2. Yuri Shur, Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, University of Alaska Fairbanks
3. Vladimir Romanovsky, Geophysical Institute and Department of Geology/Geography, University of Alaska Fairbanks
4. Tim Hammond, Central Yukon Field Office, Bureau of Land Management
5. James Partain, NOAA Alaska Regional Climate Service
6. Jimmy Fox, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
7. John Chythlook, Alaska Department of Fish and Game
8. John Burr, Alaska Department of Fish and Game
9. Amy Breen, Scenarios Network for Alaska Planning (SNAP)
10. Bob Schneider, Bureau of Land Management – Fairbanks District
11. Marie Lowe, Institute of Social and Economic Research (ISER) – University of Alaska Anchorage
12. Dan Bogan, Alaska Natural Heritage Program

- Paul Krabacher, LCC Steering Committee and the Bureau of Land Management Rapid Ecoregional Assessment
- Keith Boggs, AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA (Contractor for BLM Rapid Ecoregional Assessment)
- Margaret King, Margaret J King & Associates
- Susan Fox, Helen Wiggins, and Julie Griswold, Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS, Facilitation)

Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)

Kotzebue Meeting

Tuesday, 9 November 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western Alaska LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion – The meeting was opened for questions and discussion on the LCC.

A. Data and Science Needs

- There are two critical data needs for the Selawik National Wildlife Refuge (<http://selawik.fws.gov/>):
 - Permafrost – mapping where permafrost exists, understanding and predicting changes in permafrost, and predicting potential impacts of warming/thawing permafrost (e.g., effects on infrastructure). This is a good issue for a partnership like the LCC because this is a need that exists on a broader regional scale.
 - Topographic/elevation data – the refuge is currently working with older USGS topographic maps; there is a need for high-resolution topographic mapping and elevation models (e.g., using LIDAR).
- There is an overall need for basic regional baseline data, but it is more than any individual agency can afford.
- Information on subsistence is extremely important in the local communities, including information on present and future populations of subsistence species (e.g., caribou, moose, walrus, seals, etc.) and patterns of use. Both biological and social science data are needed to help management agencies make subsistence decisions.
- Caribou is a critical species in the area (the Western Arctic Caribou Herd) – need more data on migration patterns, relative effects of change drivers such as climate and human activities:
 - Recently, caribou have been migrating south later, creating a mismatch in timing for harvest.
 - Could do "social network" research methodology on caribou (e.g., examining how caribou decide to use various habitat).
 - There is a Western Arctic Caribou Working Group, which includes representatives from all villages in the region (it is not an agency group); they exchange information on the caribou herd and help identify research needs for agencies.

- Data on hydrology and water resources is needed:
 - Water transportation issues (e.g., ability of fuel barges to reach villages) are important – need to understand possible changes in river levels and impact on transportation.
 - Also need to understand how possible changes in river levels may affect fish species.
- Animal health and disease is a concern – how climate change may affect wildlife health and disease (including diseases that could pass to humans).
- Would be useful to have information to help inform feasibility of alternative power development (solar, wind, etc.).
- Ocean/marine issues of concern include:
 - How might sea level rise affect this region and specific towns/villages?
 - Need a better understanding and detailed mapping of coastal erosion.
 - Need to understand possible effects of ocean acidification in the region.
 - Need to understand possible effects of climate change on marine mammal populations, which are important for subsistence.
- Need information that would help inform decisions on whether to introduce wood bison to the region.
- Need some sort of "clearinghouse" where interested parties can access scientific data and information.

B. Potential Partnerships, Relevant Groups, and Efforts

- Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK)/Indigenous Knowledge should be incorporated in a meaningful way, as an integral part of research in the region:
 - Scientists coming into local communities asking for local observations and TEK should do so in a more coordinated fashion, to avoid duplication and help prevent "fatigue" in the local TEK experts.
 - Need to create parity between locals and scientists and involve TEK experts as co-equals with scientists.
 - TEK should also be used to guide research objectives, before the research is initiated.
 - Need an "umbrella" or clearinghouse of what science is being done in communities so that groups and individuals can collaborate and avoid duplication.

- The Maniilaq Association and the Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium recently convened a Climate Summit in Kotzebue to discuss climate change (note: LCC staff need to determine if there was a summary or product from this meeting).
- NANA Regional Corporation has several relevant documents, including land use and energy plans: <http://www.nana.com/>.
- The Kotzebue Indian Environmental General Assistance Program (IGAP) is an effort relevant to the LCC.
- Two relevant Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) reports from the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service:
 - *Uqausriptigun: In Our Own Words. Selawik elders speak about caribou, reindeer and life as they knew it.* Selawik National Wildlife Refuge, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2007.
 - *Iqaluich Niginaqtuat: Fish That We Eat.* U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Office of Subsistence Management, Fisheries Resource Monitoring Program. Final Report No. FIS02-023. 2006.

C. Other Issues and Questions

- Suggestion that both the LCC and REA (Rapid Ecoregional Assessment) need a transparent process for how local interests and communities will be included. Local people need to know where they have a voice and they should be at the same level of agencies for input, not just at an "advisory" level. LCC and REA should communicate clearly about how decisions in the LCC and REA are made.
- Concern that agency processes for resource management that are initiated in the lower-48 do not necessarily translate to Alaska, given local subsistence issues and cultural context.
 - Karen Murphy emphasized that the role of the LCC is *not* to weigh in on policy decisions, nor advocate for specific regulations or management processes, but only to help provide scientific information and data.
- Question on the Alaska Rapid Ecoregional Assessment (REA) and why the specific REA geographic region was chosen (note: REA meeting was held after LCC meeting).
 - Paul Krabacher, REA Lead (Bureau of Land Management) responded that the REA is a national effort; this region was chosen for the Alaska REA primarily because of the Western Arctic Caribou Herd wintering ground. But it is important to note that the caribou use a much broader geographic range and cross into arctic Alaska, so this is a good example of a topic where different efforts and groups across western and arctic Alaska will need to collaborate.

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Elizabeth Moore, Northwest Arctic Leadership Team (NWALT)- NANA Regional Corporation
2. Lincoln Saito, Northwest Arctic Borough
3. LeeAnne Ayres, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service - Selawik National Wildlife Refuge
4. Anne Orlando, U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service - Selawik National Wildlife Refuge
5. Alex Whiting, Native Village of Kotzebue (NVOK)
6. Charlie Nazuruk, Noorvik Native Community
7. Lonnie Tebbits, Noorvik Native Community
8. John Erlich, Sr., Bureau of Land Management - Kotzebue Field Office
9. Shelly Jacobson, Central Yukon Field Office - Bureau of Land Management
10. Bibianna Scott, NANA Regional Corporation
11. Paul Eaton, Maniilaq Association

LCC and REA Staff and Contractors:

LCC:

Karen Murphy, Western AK LCC Coordinator; Greg Balogh, Arctic LCC Coordinator; Susan Fox and Helen Wiggins, Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S. (ARCUS)

REA:

Paul Krabacher, REA Lead; Margaret King, MJKing and Associates; Keith Boggs, UAA/AK Natural Heritage Program; Dan Bogan, UAA; Tobias Schwoerer, Institute for Social and Economic Research (ISER)/UAA.

**Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC)
Nome Meeting**

Wednesday, 10 November 2010

Summary Meeting Notes

I. Introductions (Susan Fox, ARCUS, Facilitator; see participant list at end of notes)

II. Western AK Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Presentation (Karen Murphy, Western Alaska LCC Coordinator)

III. Open Discussion – The meeting was opened for questions and discussion on the LCC.

A. General LCC Questions and Discussion

- Question on how LCC projects will be funded:
 - Karen responded that the LCC may receive \$1M/year specifically for LCC projects. In addition, a main goal of the LCC is to leverage other agency funding and efforts, so it is expected that additional capacity will be available through budgeting processes not specific to the LCC. For example, the U.S. Geological Survey's Alaska Climate Science Center will also have funds for research, a portion of which will be used on science priorities identified through the five Alaska LCCs.
- Question on whether there will be LCC sub-groups for specific geographic areas within the broader LCC boundary:
 - Karen responded that the format of sub- or working groups is still in discussion by the interim Steering Committee; for example, groups could be formed around specific geographic areas, taxonomic groups, by topical themes, or some combination thereof.
- Question on whether the final LCC Steering Committee could include local community representation:
 - Karen responded that the Steering Committee will be comprised of federal and state agency representatives, but there will be other opportunities for expanded partnerships, such as in the working groups.
- A concern was voiced that agency staff might not have the time to participate in new efforts such as the LCC, even though it is clear the LCC has value:
 - Karen responded that the LCC staff recognize this concern, and the LCC will strive to avoid adding work for agency staff. It is inevitable that some additional work from agency staff will be necessary – particularly during the start up years, but the expectation is that the benefits of that work should assist the agencies in being more effective on their conservation efforts. The LCC should help agencies be more efficient and may provide additional

capacity for existing efforts. The challenge will be for the LCC to identify efforts already in agency work-plans that align with LCC priorities, and then find specific ways to support those efforts.

- Suggestion that the LCC might consider focusing on a keystone or "flagship" species or topic (i.e., similar to how brown pelican is used in the lower-48) to help the public and other partners understand the function of the LCC and to gain broad support.
- Question on how the broader public will be engaged, and suggestion that the LCC needs to make itself relevant and understood by the public to entrain broad support:
 - Karen responded that there are not any concrete plans yet for public outreach and communication, but they are thinking about opportunities for students and similar educational activities. The LCC Steering Committee recognizes the need to find ways to be relevant to the partner agencies and to the public through early successes.

B. Data and Information Needs

- There is a need for detailed spatial data on land ownership, as the area around Nome has very complex land ownership patterns.
- Subsistence is an important issue and an area of concern for many people. Specific topics that would benefit from improved information include potential changes in distance people have to travel for subsistence hunts, and changing patterns/availability of subsistence species (plant and animal). There is also a need for cultural/ethnographic data to better understand subsistence use.
- Caribou is a particularly important species; there is a need to understand how caribou populations and habitat are changing, as well as the natural cycles of caribou abundance. It will also be important to determine how issues identified by the Western Arctic Caribou Herd Working Group could be acted upon, as they have no research funding or personnel.
- There is an overall lack of historical baseline data that could be used to determine what changes are occurring on the landscape.
- Local residents have seen changes in vegetation and an increase in shrubs, but there is a lack of empirical data.
- Data and predictions on fire frequency are needed, since fire is an important factor driving landscape vegetation patterns.
- There is a need to understand how changes in precipitation may affect water resources in local communities, such as drinking water.

- Permafrost and permafrost change is recognized as an important issue and an area that needs additional research.
- Coastal erosion is a concern in many villages in the region.

IV. Meeting Participants

1. Eileen Bechtol, City of Nome (City Planner)
2. Peter Bente, Alaska Department of Fish and Game
3. Jeanette Pomrenke, National Park Service – Bering Land Bridge National Preserve
4. Dan Reed, Alaska Department of Fish and Game – Sport Fish (*Attended the Rapid Ecoregional Assessment [REA] discussion after the LCC meeting*)

LCC and REA Staff and Contractors:

Karen Murphy (LCC Coordinator), Susan Fox, Helen Wiggins (ARCUS), Paul Krabacher (BLM/REA), Keith Boggs (UAA); Dan Bogan (UAA), Tobias Schwoerer (UAA), Margaret King (MJKing and Associates)

Appendix B. Western Alaska Landscape Conservation Cooperative (LCC) Local Meeting Participants

Last Name	First Name	Organization	Meeting Attended
Petersen	Margaret	USGS	Cold Bay
Dau	Niels	n/a	Cold Bay
Derksen	Dirk	USGS	Cold Bay
Muller	Tammy	n/a	Cold Bay
Lloyd	Geoffrey	n/a	Cold Bay
Bohl	Audrey	USFWS	Cold Bay
Ikis	Didem	n/a	Cold Bay
Donnelly	Tyrone	USGS	Cold Bay
Muller	Franz	USFWS	Cold Bay
Peterson	Ken	n/a	Cold Bay
Casler	Bruce	USFWS	Cold Bay
Hoffman	Nancy	USFWS	Cold Bay
Wenger	Haim	n/a	Cold Bay
Lopez	Jorge	n/a	Cold Bay
Berg	Spencer	USFWS	Cold Bay
Ferguson	Gary	n/a	Cold Bay
Seitz	Jody	City of Dillingham	Dillingham
Novak	Celeste	BB CSRA	Dillingham
Swaim	Michael	USFWS	Dillingham
King	Lorraine	Ekwoq Village Council	Dillingham
Lisac	Mark	USFWS	Dillingham
Dyasuk	Jon	USFWS	Dillingham
Krieg	Ted	AKDFG	Dillingham
Anderson	Norm	BBNA	Dillingham
Nielsen	Duncan	USFWS	Dillingham
Dye	Jason	AKDFG	Dillingham
Woolington	Jim	AKDFG	Dillingham
Liedberg	Paul	AKDFG	Dillingham
Loiland	Jim	NCRS	Dillingham
Underwood	Tevis	USFWS	Dillingham
Woods	Frank	BBNA	Dillingham
Masley	Michele	Bristol Bay Campus	Dillingham
Lind	Orville	USFWS	King Salmon
Savage	Susan	USFWS	King Salmon
Pinnix	Julie	USFWS	King Salmon
Schaff	Bill	USFWS	King Salmon
Brady	Michael	USFWS	King Salmon
Greanya	Marla	USFWS	King Salmon
Boshers	Amanda	USFWS	King Salmon
Pecen	Stacey	USFWS	King Salmon
Britton	Ron	USFWS	King Salmon
Hamon	Troy	NPS	King Salmon
Turner	Carissa	NPS	King Salmon
Brubaker	Mike	AK Native Tribal Health Consortium	Anchorage
Rea	Caryn	Conoco Phillips	Anchorage
Dutton	Karla	Defenders of Wildlife	Anchorage
Shepard	Michael	NPS	Anchorage
Rosa	Cheryl	USARC	Anchorage
Payne	John	North Slope Science Initiative	Anchorage
Loya	Wendy	The Wilderness Society	Anchorage
Williams	Dee	BOEMRE	Anchorage
Warnick	Nils	Audubon Alaska	Anchorage
Zack	Steve	Wildlife Conservation Society	Anchorage
Howell	Dave	BLM	Anchorage
McAfee	Steph	The Wilderness Society	Anchorage
Daigneault	Mike	AKDFG	Anchorage
Clemant	Joel	Wilburforce Foundation	Anchorage
Hartsig	Andrew	Ocean Conservancy	Anchorage
McTeague	Monica	AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA	Anchorage
Myers	Eric	Audubon Alaska	Anchorage
Streever	Bill	BP	Anchorage
Shasby	Mark	USGS	Anchorage
Jacobson	Cindi	USFWS	Anchorage

Last Name	First Name	Organization	Meeting Attended
K'eit (Holzinger)	Kristin	BIA	Anchorage
McAfee	June	Calista Corp.	Anchorage
Witten	Evie	The Nature Conservancy	Anchorage
Sanzone	Diane	BP	Anchorage
Leonetti	Crystal	USFWS	Anchorage
Foy	Robert	NOAA-NMFS	Kodiak
Nemeth	Matt	AKDFG	Kodiak
Sundseth	Kent	USFWS	Kodiak
Wheeler	Gary	USFWS	Kodiak
VanHatten, Jr.	G. Kevin	USFWS	Kodiak
Cobb	McCrea	USFWS	Kodiak
LeBeau	Michelle	District	Kodiak
Studebaker	Stacy	Kodiak Audubon	Kodiak
Pyle	Bill	USFWS	Kodiak
Van Daele	Larry	AKDFG	Kodiak
Polito	Lisa	USFWS	Kodiak
Morriss	Charisa	USFWS	Bethel
Doolittle	Thomas	USFWS	Bethel
Gabrielson	Melissa	USFWS	Bethel
Sowl	Kristine	USFWS	Bethel
Trainor	Sarah	AACAP/SNAP	Fairbanks
Shur	Yuri	Dept. of Civil & Environmental Engineering, UAF	Fairbanks
Romanovsky	Vladimir	GI, UAF	Fairbanks
Hammond	Tim	BLM	Fairbanks
Partain	James	NOAA Alaska Regional Climate Service	Fairbanks
Fox	Jimmy	USFWS	Fairbanks
Chythlook	John	AKDFG	Fairbanks
Burr	John	AKDFG	Fairbanks
Breen	Amy	SNAP	Fairbanks
Schneider	Bob	BLM	Fairbanks
Lowe	Marie	ISER, UAA	Fairbanks
Bogan	Dan	AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA	Fairbanks
Moore	Elizabeth	NWALT, NANA Regional Corp.	Kotzebue
Saito	Lincoln	Northwest Arctic Borough	Kotzebue
Ayers	LeeAnne	USFWS	Kotzebue
Orlando	Anne	USFWS	Kotzebue
Whiting	Alex	NVOK	Kotzebue
Nazuruk	Charlie	Noorvik Native Community	Kotzebue
Tebbits	Lonnie	Noorvik Native Community	Kotzebue
Erlich, Sr.	John	BLM	Kotzebue
Jacobson	Shelly	BLM	Kotzebue
Scott	Bibianna	NANA Regional Corp.	Kotzebue
Eaton	Paul	Manilaq Assoc.	Kotzebue
Bechtol	Eileen	City of Nome	Nome
Bente	Peter	AKDFG	Nome
Pomrenke	Jeanette	NPS	Nome
Reed	Dan	AKDFG	Nome
Staff/Contractors:			
Murphy	Karen	USFWS	LCC
Balogh	Greg	USFWS	LCC
Reynolds	Joel	USFWS	LCC
Krabacher	Paul	BLM	REA
Boggs	Keith	AK Natural Heritage Program/UAA	REA
King	Margaret	Margaret J King & Assoc.	REA
Bogan	Dan	UAA	REA
Schwoerer	Tobias	ISER, UAA	REA
Fox	Susan	ARCUS	LCC
Wiggins	Helen	ARCUS	LCC

